

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18704022

Test Anxiety As Correlate Of Academic Achievement Among Public Secondary School Students In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined test anxiety as correlate of academic achievement among public secondary school students in Delta State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 37,263 students in the 409 public secondary schools in Delta State. The sample size used for the study comprised 396 students drawn from the population of the study. The sample size was drawn using Taro Yamane formula. Cluster sampling technique was used to select the sample. Two instruments were used to collect data for the study namely; Test Anxiety Questionnaire (TAQ) and Students Academic Achievement (SAA) scores which were obtained from the teacher made test. Face and construct validation of the instruments were established by three experts from the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State. The reliability was established using Cronbach Alpha and the computation yielded value such as: 0.79 for TAQ. The data collected were analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS, v.26). Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) was employed to answer research questions and t- test of significance was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Simple regression analysis was employed to determine the relationship among the variables. The findings of the study revealed that in general, the relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable were positively or negatively low. However, the results showed that there was also a statistically significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement (0.134) of public secondary school students in Delta State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that school teachers should adopt supportive assessment strategies, provide clear instructions, and foster a positive classroom environment to help students feel confident without experiencing pressure. The study contributed to knowledge by providing better understanding of the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of secondary school students.

Keywords: Test Anxiety, Academic Achievement, Gender

INTRODUCTION

Academic achievement is a term used to describe an individual's achievement on subjects taught and tested in school. It is the overall measure of cognitive, affective and psychomotor accomplishments of a student with which they are judged academically fit or unfit (Okafor et al,2018). More so, Oguezi et al.,2019 viewed academic achievement as students scholastic ability and attainment, which signifies the

overall level of knowledge they have acquired in school, a subject, or in a particular learning activity, process or situation and that student's academic achievement occupied a vital position in the educational system. Academic achievement refers to achievement outcomes that indicate how far a person has progressed in specific goals of activities in instructional settings, such as school, college and university (Suleiman, 2023). It is measured through examinations and continuous assessment. The outcome of these examinations or assessment serves as a pointer to the direction of their achievement, whether positive or negative.

Over the years, Mathematics and English Language failures among secondary school students has been on the increase. These failures among secondary school students can stem from other interrelated factors, and several prominent causes which include: Lack of parental involvement, parental engagement which significantly influence student's academic achievement. When parents are less involved in the academic performance of their children, whether due to socioeconomic factors, lack of education themselves, or other commitments, students may receive less academic support and guidance. This can lead to lower motivation and poorer academic outcomes (Fan & Williams, 2018). Research indicates that active parental engagement in a child's education significantly boosts academic achievement (Hill & Tyson, 2022). Poor school environment, unsupported homes or school can negatively impact student's academic achievement. Distractions in the home or school environment can hinder focus and learning. A negative school climate, characterized by bullying, inadequate resources, and low teacher-student relationship, can lead to poor academic achievement. A supportive and safe school environment is essential for student success. A positive school climate fosters academic achievement by creating engaging and supportive educational experiences (Thapa et al., 2020). Mental health problems such as anxiety, depression, and stress are prevalent among adolescents and can significantly impair academic achievement. Mental health can lead to absenteeism, lack of focus, and reduced motivation to engage in schoolwork. Student's mental health status significantly affects their academic achievement. (Suldo & Shaunessy, 2021).

Academic achievement remains a central concern in educational discourse, serving as an essential indicator of students' learning outcomes and the effectiveness of the school system. In Nigeria, and particularly in Delta State, persistent reports of students underachievement in both internal and external examinations have raised serious concern among educators, parents, and policymakers. Despite government efforts at curriculum reform, teacher training, and provision of instructional materials, students in many public secondary schools have continue to record unsatisfactory academic results. This worrisome trend suggests that variables beyond cognitive ability may significantly contribute to students academic success or failure. Consequently, attention has shifted towards understanding the role of psychological factors such as test anxiety in shaping students academic achievement.

Test anxiety is an unpleasant emotion defined by fear or feeling apprehensive. It is evident that shows when one is worried and has some concern over an issue (Bada & Idoko, 2021). Chanchal et al. (2021) defined anxiety as a nervous system-excited condition in which a person is experiencing tension, nervousness, and worry. Hence, anxiety may simply be defined as an innate psychological trait in individuals usually associated with tension and nervousness. Bada and Idoko (2021) defined test anxiety as a negative emotion characterized by fear or feeling apprehensive towards evaluation. It is a combination of symptoms that interfere with one's desire or capacity to perform well on tests which can be physical, psychological, emotional, or mental (Nwafor et al., 2023). Hence, test anxiety may simply be defined as fear, anxiety or anxiousness expressed by students towards all forms of tests.

Test anxiety, according to Galle et al. (2020), has been overwhelmingly identified as a two-factor construct, consisting of the cognitive (often referred to as worry) and emotional (or affective) components. Comprehensively, Zeidner (2023) asserted that test anxiety has four components: behavioral, cognitive, emotional, and physical. While the behavioral components consist of feeling of restlessness and fidgeting during tests, the cognitive consists of mental activity occurring during the testing setting which includes among others negative thoughts, fear of failure and its consequences, poor understanding of question and difficulty in reading. The emotional components consists fear, tension, apprehension, test/examination nervousness and somatic symptoms like shortness of breath, rapid heartbeat, stomach

aches, headaches, excessive sweating, nausea, perspiration among others while the physical components includes procrastination, dodging of work and poor study skills. Considering these components, one can posit that test anxiety is a significant factor that influences students' academic achievement in all forms of examinations as any of its listed components is bound to manifest among students before, during or after a test.

Gender appears to play a role in academic achievement, subtly influencing educational experiences and learning outcomes in complex ways. Gender is a generic term that classifies into male and female those identifiable characteristics exhibited by the human population. The influence of gender can be seen in classroom dynamics and societal expectations, which collectively contribute to the academic achievement of students. In classroom settings, gender dynamics often influence student participation and achievement in some subjects, especially science and mathematics. Allahnana et al., (2018) in their study on Assessment of Gender and Interest in Mathematics achievement in Keffi Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria found that there was a significant difference between mean achievement scores of male and female students in Mathematics. Male students outperformed their female counterparts in Mathematics. Ani et al., (2020) observed that male students performed better than their female counterparts in Basic Science.

The researcher has identified the various root causes of underachievement among senior secondary school students in Delta State, and is also interested in bridging the gap by proffering workable solutions that will help reduce and curb the menace of underachievement among secondary students in Delta State. It is therefore, against this background that the researcher channels its interest in finding out, to what extent test anxiety, emotional intelligence and metacognitive awareness are correlates of academic achievement among public secondary school students in Delta State. The findings of this study are expected to provide empirical evidence that will guide educational stakeholders in designing interventions aimed at reducing test anxiety, fostering emotional intelligence, and enhancing metacognitive skills among students for improved academic outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

The persistent decline in the academic achievement of public secondary school students in Delta State has become a major concern for educators, parents, and other stakeholders in the education sector. Despite sustained government efforts to improve educational quality, many students continue to perform poorly in both internal and external examinations. This situation suggests that factors beyond infrastructural development and curriculum reforms may be influencing students' academic outcomes.

One important psychological factor that has received limited attention within Nigeria's educational system is test anxiety. Test anxiety adversely affects students' emotional, cognitive, and physiological functioning, thereby disrupting concentration, memory recall, and effective problem-solving during examinations. Students with high levels of test anxiety often find it difficult to cope with examination pressure, which results in poor study habits, low self-confidence, and persistent academic underachievement. As a result, many students are unable to display their true academic abilities.

This study focuses on test anxiety as a key psychological factor influencing the academic achievement of public secondary school students in Delta State. The topic is chosen because test anxiety remains under-researched in the local context, despite its strong link to students' examination performance and overall academic success. By examining this issue, the study seeks to fill the gap in existing literature by providing empirical evidence on the role of test anxiety in students' academic achievement, thereby offering insights that can guide educators, school counselors, and policymakers in developing effective intervention strategies.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate test anxiety as correlate of academic achievement among senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta State.
2. Find out the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of male and female senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Significance of the Study

This study has both theoretical and practical significance. Theoretically, the study was anchored on Spielberger (1966) test anxiety theory.

Spielberger (1966) test anxiety theory, suggests that test anxiety can influence the performance of a student on a test regardless of the individual's ability. A student high in test anxiety is preoccupied with negative thoughts and uncomfortably feelings before an examination. The cognitive distortion can lead to flight of thought, resulting in poor performance of the test.

Practically, the findings of the study would be of great significance to students, teachers, examination conducting bodies, (such as West African Examination Council, WAEC; and National Examination Council, NECO), curriculum planners, parents, educational psychologists, guidance counselors and future researchers.

Students at all levels of educational system will benefit from the findings of the study through orientation ceremonies, seminars, and workshops. They would be guided to learn the different social interaction strategies and how to apply them when relating with people around them. This would enable them have control over their behavior, that would motivate them to remain engaged in their studies and to acquire good study skills. Students that are doing well in their studies would continue to do well and also achieve high grades academically. The underachievers would pick up and control their behaviors by adapting positive attitude towards their academic engagement. They would also be guided to change their poor reading habits and have less test anxiety for higher academic achievement.

Examination Conducting Bodies, such as WAEC will gain from the findings of this study to improve in their methods of conducting senior secondary school certification examination. This would be done through workshops and annual meeting of the Nigeria National Committee (NCC) of the West African Examination Council WAEC, where they would determine high achievers and low achievers. Merit awards will be given to best WASSCE candidates for the year. Low achievers will be motivated to overcome test anxiety by managing their emotions, and determine to study harder for high academic achievement.

Educational psychologists stand to benefit from the findings of this study through workshops and seminars and would be aware that students who behaved and interact properly will sustain their interest in learning, and would not suffer from test anxiety. They should have this in mind when constructing test for students so as to abide by the ethical standards of testing and test construction and administration, so that the test would elicit the required information needed to improve both psychological and academic problem if students for higher academic achievement.

The findings of this study when made available through seminars, workshops, published journals would help guidance counselors address academic challenges, promote effective coping strategies and foster a hitch free environment. This would enable them contribute significantly to student's successful adaptation to the academic rigors of school engagement, social interaction and overcoming test/ examination anxiety.

Scope of the Study

The study was conducted among senior secondary two (SS2) students in public secondary schools in Delta State. The study in its' content investigated test anxiety as correlate of academic achievement in English Language and Mathematics of senior secondary two (SS2) school students. Moderator variable such as gender was examined.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta State?
2. What is the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of male and female senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There will be no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta.
2. There will be no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of male and female senior secondary two (SS2) students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Delta State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 37,263 students in the 409 public secondary schools in Delta State. The sample size used for the study comprised 396 students drawn from the population of the study. The sample size was drawn using Taro Yamane formula. Cluster sampling technique was used to select the sample. Two instruments were used to collect data for the study namely; Test Anxiety Questionnaire (TAQ), and Students Academic Achievement (SAA) scores which were obtained from the teacher made test. Face and construct validation of the instruments were established by three experts from the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State. The reliability was established using Cronbach Alpha and the computation yielded value such as: 0.79 for TAQ. The data collected were analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS, v.26). Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) was employed to answer research questions and t- test of significance was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Simple regression analysis was employed to determine the relationship among the variables. The findings of the study revealed that in general, the relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable were either positively or negatively low. However, the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of public secondary school students is statistically significant (0.134). Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that school teachers should adopt supportive assessment strategies, provide clear instructions, and foster a positive classroom environment to help students feel confident without experiencing pressure. The study contributed to knowledge by providing better understanding of the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of secondary school students. It also helped in identifying the most predictive factors of students' academic achievement which would help in prioritizing educational interventions.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

Data collected were analyzed based on the research questions and null hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The results are presented in tables below to highlight the findings.

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of senior secondary students (SS2) in public secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 1: Pearson (r) on the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of Senior Secondary Students in Public Secondary Schools

Source Of Variation		Test Anxiety	Academic Achievement	Remark
TEST ANXIETY	Pearson Correlation	1	.134	Low positive relationship
	N	302	302	
ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	Pearson Correlation	.134	1	
	N	302	302	

The results presented in Table 1 show the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) between test anxiety and academic achievement among Senior Secondary students (SS2) in public secondary schools in Delta State. The correlation coefficient is $r = .134$, indicating a low positive relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of male and female senior secondary (SS2) students in public secondary schools in Delta State?*

Table 2: Pearson (r) on The Relationship between Test Anxiety and Academic Achievement of Male and Female Senior Secondary (SS2) Students in Public Secondary Schools in Delta State.

GENDER			TEST ANXIETY	ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	REMARK
MALE	TEST ANXIETY	Pearson Correlation	1	.173*	Low positive relationship
		N	194	194	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.016		
FEMALE	TEST ANXIETY	Pearson Correlation	1	.021	Very low positive relationship
		N	108	108	
	ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	Pearson Correlation	.021	1	
		N	108	108	

The results in Table 4 show the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) between test anxiety and academic achievement among male and female Senior Secondary (SS2) students in public secondary schools. For male students, the correlation coefficient is $r = 0.173$, indicating a low positive relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement. This suggests that as test anxiety increases, academic achievement slightly improves for male students, though the effect is small. For female students, the correlation

coefficient is $r = 0.021$, indicating a very low positive relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement.

Testing the Null hypotheses

Null Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of senior secondary (SS2) students in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Table 1: Pearson (r) Test of Significance of the Relationship between Test Anxiety and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary (SS2) Students in Public Secondary Schools in Delta State.

Source Of Variation		Test Anxiety	Academic Achievement	Remark
TEST ANXIETY	Pearson Correlation	1	.134*	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.019	
	N	302	302	
ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	Pearson Correlation	.134*	1	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.019		
	N	302	302	

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

Finding in Table 8 revealed correlation coefficient ($r = 0.134$), with $p\text{-value} = 0.019$, which is less than 0.05, meaning that the relationship is statistically significant. This means that the observed correlation is unlikely to have occurred by chance. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of senior secondary (SS2) students in public secondary schools in Delta State is rejected.

Null Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of male and female senior secondary (SS2) students in public secondary schools in Delta State.

Table 2: Pearson (r) Test of significance of the Relationship between Test Anxiety and Academic Achievement of Male and Female Senior Secondary (SS2) Students in Public Secondary Schools in Delta State.

GENDER			TEST ANXIETY	ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	REMARK
MALE	TEST ANXIETY	Pearson Correlation	1	.173*	Significant
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.016	
		N	194	194	
	ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	Pearson Correlation	.173*	1	Significant
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.016		
		N	194	194	
FEMALE	TEST ANXIETY	Pearson Correlation	1	.021	Not Significant
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.833	
		N	108	108	
	ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT	Pearson Correlation	.021	1	Not Significant
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.833		
		N	108	108	

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

The results in Table 11 revealed that for male students, the correlation coefficient was $r = 0.173$, with a p-value of 0.016, indicating a low but statistically significant positive relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement. For female students, the correlation coefficient was $r = 0.021$, with a p-value of 0.833, indicating a very low and statistically insignificant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of male SS2 students in public secondary schools in Delta State while there is no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement of female SS2 students.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study examined test anxiety as correlate of academic achievement among public senior secondary school two (SS2) students in Delta State.

The result of the first hypothesis shows that there was a significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement among public senior secondary school two (SS2) students in Delta State. This implies that the level of anxiety students experience during tests has a measurable effect on how well they perform academically. High test anxiety can impair concentration, reduce working memory and lower confidence, often leading to poor performance. Conversely, low or manageable anxiety levels may motivate students to prepare better and achieve higher scores. The result of the this study supported the work of Ilo and Unachukwu (2020), who noted that test anxiety significantly predicted academic achievement of students especially in Mathematics and English Language in Anambra State. Similarly, Okobia and Oji (2021, found that test anxiety significantly influenced academic achievement.

The result of the second hypothesis showed a low positive significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement in male students and very low positive non-significant relationship between the variables in female SS2 students. This means that for the male students, there was a statistically significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement. This might be due to a small amount of test anxiety acting as motivation and pushing the students to prepare better and perform slightly better in academics. There was no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement among female students. This difference implied that test anxiety might have influenced male and female students differently, possibly due to variations on how they experience or manage stress during exams. Understanding these gender differences is essential for educators and psychologists seeking to support students in managing anxiety and optimizing academic success. The result of the findings was supported by Gidado and Zubair (2025), who noted that there existed significant differences between male and female students test anxiety in senior secondary schools in south- west, Nigeria.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was established that there was a low statistically significant influence of test anxiety on academic achievement among public senior secondary school two (SS2) students in Delta State, despite their weak correlations.

Recommendations

1. School teachers should adopt supportive assessment strategies, provide clear instructions, and foster a positive classroom environment to help students feel confident without overwhelming pressure. Regular workshops on time management, relaxation techniques, and exam preparation can also help students develop coping skills that enhance performance while minimizing harmful effects of excessive anxiety.
2. Schools should implement gender-sensitive approaches to managing test anxiety. Since a small amount of anxiety may serve as a motivator, particularly for male students, interventions should aim to balance pressure and support. For female students, the very low relationship suggests that anxiety may not significantly impact performance, but support is still essential. Teachers and counselors should provide stress-reduction techniques, exam preparation workshops, and safe spaces for open discussions about academic pressures.

Parents should be sensitized on the negative effects of excessive pressure and unrealistic expectations on students' academic performance. Instead, parents should provide emotional support, encouragement, and a calm home environment, especially during examination periods, to help reduce test anxiety.

Students should be encouraged to maintain healthy lifestyles, including adequate sleep, balanced nutrition, and regular physical exercise. These healthy habits help regulate stress levels, improve concentration, and reduce test anxiety, which in turn enhances academic achievement.

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